

Effects of Different Growing Media on the Germination of Umzimbeet (*Milletia grandis* S.) Seeds

Aluko Ahmed Kayode
Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

Abstract

This project examined the effect of different growing media on the germination of Umzimbeet (*Milletia grandis*) was conducted within the premises of Federal College of Forestry (FRIN), Jericho, Ibadan, Oyo State. Top soils, clay, sawdust, river sand were used. Treatments were arranged in Complete Randomized Design (CRD) and replicated three times. Data were collected on plant height, numbers of leaves for 5 weeks. The results show that there is low effect on growing media involving sawdust, but has a high effect on growing media involving much sand and a little clay, therefore; it shows that T₉ is the best growth medium for the sprouting and germination of *Milletia grandis* through seed with an average of 16.612 on plant height. Although T₅ = Sand + Sawdust (2:1) with an average of 12.158 on stem diameter and T₁ = Top soil has the best according to the leaf count with an average of 6.261. T₉=sand and clay (2:1) was observed as the best growing medium for germination and sprouting of Umzimbeet (*Milletia grandis*) seed.

Keywords: Umzimbeet, media, germination, sawdust, leaf count, FRIN, Bamboo plantation.

Received: 22/07/18

Accepted: 14/10/18

Introduction

Tree planting is grounded in forest science, and if performed properly can result in the successful regeneration of a deforested area, because trees remove carbon dioxide from the air as they grow, tree planting can be used as a geo-engineering technique to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, there are trees for shade and shelter, trees that provide fruits and nuts, ornamental trees and

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

flowering trees, deciduous and evergreen. They come in all shapes and sizes from tiny dwarfs to the towering Redwoods, windswept bristlecone to whimsical topiary. Trees exist in all but the very driest or coldest regions of the world. (Obiri, 2002).

The genus '*Millettia*' plant appears in the African official book describing medicines and other studies of effect of chemical compounds on living animals and also on the use and effects of medicinal drugs. It is then known that the plant having genus '*Millettia*' is a traditional (local) herbal or medicinal tree which is having a wide range of biological activities such as anti-tumoral, anti-inflammatory, anti-viral, bactericidal, insecticidal, and pest destroying. (Labat, 1995).

The confirmation of the traditional pharmacology activities must be systemized, with reproducible procedures, in order to validate the traditional herbal formulations. The development of increasingly pointed techniques for pharmacology studies can help to widen the therapeutic spectrum of '*Millettia*'. The various species are sometimes difficult to recognize by the local populations (Hutchinson, 1964)

- Family: Papilionaceae (Leguminosae - Papilionoideae, Fabaceae)
- Vernacular names: Umzimbeet, Umsimbithwa (Zulu), Kaffir, Ironwood

Millettia is named after Charles Millet of Canton, China (Daskuki, 1991) and *grandis* means large. This plant belongs to the pea and legume family Fabaceae.

Millettia grandis has a rather small area of distribution. Therefore, it may easily become liable to genetic erosion, although it is still locally common. In many regions it is already under pressure because it is a favored tree for building poles and wood carving and because many forests in its area of distribution are being cleared for agricultural land. However, it seems that Umzimbeet could sustain current levels of exploitation in some forests in South Africa. Umzimbeet occurs in coastal forest and open lowland forest up to 600 m altitude. It can be found as a pioneer along forest margins. It tolerates light frost. It often occurs on sandy soils, but also on shale, where trees are often gnarled. It grows best in deep soils where ample water is available. It is locally common. Umzimbeet occurs along the coast from eastern South Africa from North of East London in the Eastern Cape Province into KwaZulu-Natal as far as southern Mozambique (Daskuki, 1991).

Umzimbeet has several features which gives it tremendous agro-forestry potential for rural community development. It does not compete vigorously with other crops and being a Legume, it enhances soil fertility through its nitrogen fixing ability. This plant species tends to be unknown to many people, hence: this study is concerned and based on the research to know how this plant species is being propagated and the effect of the growing medium used in the sprouting of the *Millettia grandis* stem. This is because the plant species is indigenous and it is unknown to many people. Therefore, the study is aimed at determining the effect of different growing media for germination of Umzimbeet (*Millettia grandis*).

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out within the premises of Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan, located within the Government Reserve Area (GRA), Jericho, Ibadan North –West Local Government Area, Oyo State. The area lies between latitude 7°26N and longitude 3°51E. The climate pattern is tropically dominated by annual rainfall ranges from 1,300-500mm and average relative humidity of about 65 % the average temperature is about 26°C. The dry season usually commence from November to March while the raining season is usually April to October (FRIN, 2018).

Material Sources

The seeds of the *Milletia grandis* were collected under its mother at the department of Agronomy of the University of Ibadan, Ibadan; Oyo State. The top soil was collected at the *Bamboo* plantation along the way to FRIN within the college premises. However, the river sand was collected from a stream in the college premises, while the clay soil was collected from a clay heap at the *Bamboo* plantation within the school premises. The watering can and the hand trowel were gotten in the school premises, while the polythene pots were purchased from FRIN.

Methods

The collected soil clods were broken in order to loosen the weight of the soil and to soften the texture of the soil, and other unwanted materials like nylons, bottles which can serve as an obstacle to the proper penetration of the plant parts were removed from the soil. And also, the river sand was washed thoroughly and sterilized in order to get rid of parasitic organisms that might be present in the river sand which may affect the proper germination of the plant, *Milletia grandis*.

The seeds were sown at one-inch depth of a polythene pots containing different growing media according to designed treatment and was watered thrice in a week because the plant does not require much water during rainy season but it requires much in dry season (ample).

The experimental pots were filled with different growing media to their maximum level of 1.5 kg. The experiments consist of (9) treatments and a control replicated (3) times making it a total of thirty (30) pots and weekly assessment were recorded accordingly.

Experimental Design

The experiment was laid down in a Complete Randomized Design (CRD). The treatments were as follows: -

- T₁ = Top soil
- T₂ = Sand
- T₃ = Top soil + Sand (1:1)
- T₄ = Top soil + Sawdust (1:1)

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

- T₅ = Sand + Sawdust (2:1)
- T₆ = Top soil + Clay (3:1)
- T₇ = Sand + Clay (3:1)
- T₈ = Top soil + Clay (2:1)
- T₉ = Sand + Clay (2:1)
- T₁₀ = Topsoil + Sand + Sawdust (2:1:1)

PARAMETER ACCESSED

Plant Height (cm) – the plant’s height was determined with the use of a tape rule
 Numbers of leaves – the number of leaves were counted weekly
 Stem diameter – the stem diameter of the plant was measured with the use of vernier caliper.

Data Analysis

The data obtained were statistically analyzed by two-way ANOVA. Mean differences were calculated for significance by using Duncan’s test at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level.

Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows that T₁ = Top soil has the best average according to stem diameter with 6.261, T₉ = Sand + Clay (2:1) also has an average of 2.3866 and T₆ = Top soil + Clay (3:1) has the least average with 1.506. DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test) was used to separate the significance difference at 5% level of probability.

Table 1: Physical and Chemical Composition of the Soil Used

Sample Description	Loamy soil	River sand	Clay soil
%O.C	2.04	0.83	1.04
%O.M	3.51	0.25	1.79
%N	0.26	0.04	0.10
P (Mg/kg)	5.04	4.06	30.3
Mn (mg/kg)	23.7	1.06	5.9
Fe (mg/kg)	26.0	2.0	19
Cu (mg/kg)	5.3	2.6	5.9
Zn (mg/kg)	2.2	11	9.3
Na (Cmol/kg)	1.9	3.0	0.83
K (Cmol/kg)	0.05	0.21	0.10
Mg (Cmol/kg)	3.0	1.06	0.00
Ca (Cmol/kg)	7.8	0.96	2.6
Sand (%)	87.4	91.00	70.5
Clay (%)	9.1	5.0	25
Silt (%)	3.5	4.0	4.5

Source: Department Soil Laboratory, Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, 2018.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
 ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Table 3 shows that (T₉ = Sand + Clay (2:1) with an average of 16.612 of plant height through which it can be deduced that this treatment with its appropriate proportion is the best and suitable growth medium for planting this species of tree through seed, followed T₇ = Sand + Clay (3:1) with an average of 13.994 and the least average of the plant height was (T₆ = Top soil + Clay (3:1) with an average of 5.28. DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test) was used to separate the significance different at 5% level of probability.

Table 2: Effect of Growing Media on the Stem Diameter of *Milletia grandis*

TRT	Weeks					Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
T ₁	1.100	1.400	1.567	1.97	1.800	6.261
T ₂	1.100	1.500	1.633	1.800	2.00	1.606
T ₃	1.367	1.567	1.767	2.067	2.27	1.8076
T ₄	1.167	1.467	1.600	1.667	2.07	1.5942
T ₅	1.200	1.400	1.633	1.867	7.73	2.766
T ₆	1.100	1.267	1.500	1.733	1.93	1.506
T ₇	1.300	1.667	1.933	2.233	2.40	1.9066
T ₈	1.000	1.233	1.367	1.533	1.97	1.4206
T ₉	1.833	2.200	2.400	2.600	2.90	2.3866
T ₁₀	1.233	1.600	1.867	2.100	2.23	1.806

Table 4 shows that (T₅ = Sand + Sawdust (2:1) gave the best result of an average of 12.158 in terms of leaf count through which this observation can be described to the general understanding that the growth medium used for this treatment with the appropriate proportion is the suitable growth medium for this plant, followed by (T₉ = Sand + Clay (2:1) with an average of 8.998 and the least average of the leaf count; (T₆ = Top soil + Clay (3:1) with an average of 4.00. DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test) was used to separate the significant difference at 5% level of probability.

Table 3: Effect of Growth Media on the Height of *Milletia grandis*

TRT	Weeks					Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
T ₁	5.67	11.90	13.63	15.23	18.67	13.02
T ₂	1.07	6.73	9.00	9.27	12.33	7.68
T ₃	3.13	8.33	11.17	13.00	16.00	10.326
T ₄	3.33	6.77	8.93	10.03	11.50	8.112
T ₅	6.57	8.03	11.67	14.67	15.50	11.288
T ₆	3.33	4.40	5.20	6.20	7.27	5.28
T ₇	9.67	11.83	14.50	16.30	17.67	13.994
T ₈	0.90	5.67	8.00	12.30	15.67	8.508
T ₉	14.03	15.60	17.33	17.57	18.53	16.612
T ₁₀	4.00	8.33	11.17	13.50	16.00	10.6

Table 4: Effect of Growing Media on the Leaf Count of *Milletia grandis*

TRT	Weeks					Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
T ₁	1.67	7.00	8.00	10.00	10.00	7.334
T ₂	1.67	7.00	8.00	10.00	10.00	7.334
T ₃	1.33	3.67	6.67	9.67	11.67	6.602
T ₄	2.33	3.00	5.00	8.33	12.00	6.132
T ₅	6.33	8.53	11.93	16.33	17.67	12.158
T ₆	0.00	3.00	5.00	5.00	7.00	4.00
T ₇	3.00	7.00	8.67	10.33	10.33	7.868
T ₈	2.67	5.67	6.33	8.33	9.33	6.466
T ₉	5.00	9.33	10.00	10.33	10.33	8.998
T ₁₀	2.33	5.67	7.67	9.33	9.67	6.934

Conclusion

From the study, it can be deduced that seeds of *Milletia grandis* responded positively in terms of plant height, leaf count and stem diameter to various growth media used. It shows that (T₉ = sand + clay (2:1) also thrives well in the data collected, though not at the highest average in all but has a better and improved result in all; T₅ = Sand + Sawdust (2:1) and T₁ (Top soil) also produce and germinate well in the experiment done above.

References

- Dasuki, U. A., and A. M. Schot. (1991): Taxonomy of Fordia Hemsley (Papilionoideae: Millettieae). *Blumea* 36: 191-204.
- FRIN (2018). Department Soil Laboratory, Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, 2018
- Hutchinson, J. (1964): Papilionoideae: The Genera of Flowering Plants, Vol. 1, 297-489.
- Labat, J.-N., and D. J. Du Puy. (1995): New Species and Combinations In *Milletia* Wight & Arnott And *Pongamiopsis* R. Viguier (Legu- Minosae-Millettieae) From Madagascar. *Novon* 5: 171-182.
- Obiri J. Lawes, M. and Mukolwe, M., (2002): The Dynamics and Sustainable Use of High-Value Tree Species of The Coastal Pondoland Forests Of Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *Forest Ecology and Management* 166(1/3): 131–148.